

C-SCALE

D3.2 Compute federation optimised for Copernicus data analytics

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Deliverable Abstract

The C-SCALE Compute Federation delivers access to cloud and HPC/HTC resources to support Copernicus and Earth Observation related research activities. This document describes the services supported by the C-SCALE Compute Federation and how they support Copernicus and EO data analytics.

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
CO	Collaborative Organisation
C-SCALE	Copernicus - eoSC AnaLytics Engine
DIAS	Data and Information Access Services
EO	Earth Observation
EODC	Earth Observation Data Centre (C-SCALE provider)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GRNET	Greek Research and Technology Network (C-SCALE provider)
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTC	High Throughput Computing
HTDP	High Throughput Data Processing
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IAM	Identity and Management
INCD-NCG	Infraestrutura Nacional de Computação Distribuída-National Computing Grid (C-SCALE provider)
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
LDAP	Lightweight Directory Access Protocol
M2M	Machine to Machine
NREN	National Research and Education Network
OCI	Open Container Initiative
OIDC	OpenID Connect
OLA	Operational Level Agreement
PaaS	Platform as a Service
REST	Representational State Transfer
SCIM	System for Cross-domain Identity Management
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SRAM	SURF Research Access Management
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
TB	Terabyte
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VA	Virtual Access
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The C-SCALE Compute Federation brings together European commercial (e.g., Copernicus DIAS) and public (from e-infrastructure) computing providers to deliver a federated infrastructure to support Copernicus and Earth Observation (EO) use cases that deal with data- and compute-intensive workloads. The initial design of the federation was described in D3.1 Initial Design of the Compute Federation¹ and D3.3 End user documentation for batch processing system². Since then, C-SCALE has developed two services that will expand the EOSC offer for supporting processing workflows for Earth Observation data: (1) the *Federated Earth System Simulation and Data Processing Platform (FedEarthData)* and the (2) *openEO Platform*. These services are supported by the Virtual Access mechanism of C-SCALE and its usage is reported in a series of deliverables D3.4³, D3.5⁴, D3.6⁵, as well as in period assessments of the services V1, V2, and V3 respectively.

FedEarthData brings together two types of computing providers: cloud and HTC/HPC via a set of interfaces for a flexible approach to analytics: IaaS for running VMs and containers, HTC/HPC batch systems to run scalable jobs, Notebooks interface for interactive computing and openEO for an EO-specific batch-oriented processing system. These are supported by the C-SCALE federation.

openEO Platform offers a fully managed service to run EO workflows where users only need to interact with an API.

The services are in the process of onboarding in EOSC and once completed will bring these capabilities easily accessible for EOSC users from the EOSC Marketplace.

¹ D3.1 - <https://zenodo.org/record/7728609>

² D3.3 - <https://zenodo.org/record/7726196>

³ D3.4 - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7728646>

⁴ D3.5 - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7788875>

⁵ D3.6 - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7476817>

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1 Introduction

This document describes the computing services powered by the C-SCALE Compute Federation that enable users to perform Earth Observation related analytics on a distributed e-Infrastructure. The document describes in Section 2 the Federated Earth System Simulation and Data Processing Platform (FedEarthData) service, then it describes the openEO Platform in Section 3. Section 4 describes how the services interact with EOSC. Finally, conclusions are given in Section 5.

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2 FedEarthData

The Federated Earth System Simulation and Data Processing Platform (FedEarthData) is C-SCALE’s distributed infrastructure of data and compute providers supporting the execution of Earth System Simulation and Data Processing workflows at scale.

It offers a flexible cloud-based data processing capacity to create and scale data processing pipelines that run on optimised execution environments near the data. Jupyter Notebooks and openEO API offer user-friendly and intuitive processing of a wide variety of Copernicus and Earth Observation datasets on these computing providers, including the ability to integrate these data with modelling and forecasting workflows leveraging specialised compute resources.

FedEarthData builds on the design of the C-SCALE Compute Federation (see D3.1). As shown in Figure 1, through FedEarthData, the C-SCALE Compute Federation offers access to two types of computing resources:

- Cloud: IaaS (OpenStack) and container platforms (Kubernetes) with federated orchestration for the deployment of applications and platforms across providers in a seamless way. These providers deliver a very flexible and customisable computing platform where users have complete control over the software and the supporting compute capacity. This flexibility of the computing platform enables the support of a variety of workloads: user gateways or portals, interactive computing platforms, and data- and/or compute-intensive workloads.
- HPC and HTC: large, shared computing systems for generic batch processing via a jobs queue that is managed by a workload scheduler (e.g., Slurm). These systems are efficient and highly optimized IT solutions for data- and/or compute-intensive workloads that do not require privileged access or on-demand resources. These solutions empower users to distribute their jobs over many hardware nodes, whilst their shared nature enables high utilization of these compute resources.

Figure 1. C-SCALE Compute Federation

The use cases that C-SCALE expects to cater to are generally those that span several countries and thus institutions. In order to make working together on those use cases and the management as

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easy as possible for its members, C-SCALE has opted to use collaboration tools where groups and members are easily managed. This is achieved by a central component that orchestrates the interaction between Identity Providers (IdPs), users and Service Providers (SPs) in an as seamless as possible manner. A benefit for users is that they keep using the credentials they already have from their home institution. This also enhances security as they do not have to choose a new username and password. This way, users can make use of the, hopefully strong, password they have at their institution and do not have to choose yet another new and possibly weaker password for the Service Providers. C-SCALE uses an EOSC-compliant Federated Authentication and Authorisation infrastructure (AAI) relying on EGI Check-in⁶ and SURF SRAM⁷ for enabling easy access to services and shared resources. EGI Check-in is being used for Cloud providers, while SURF Research Access Management (SRAM) is used for HTP/HPC providers. While currently the cloud and HTC/HPC providers use separate AAI systems for access, there is ongoing activity to harmonize access to both Cloud and HPC/HTC resources. In this context we are investigating if we can use SRAM as a community AAI for EGI Check-in, thereby allowing SRAM-hosted CO members to use their SRAM federated identity to access both HPC/HTC and Cloud resources.

In the following subsections, each of the FedEarthData components is described.

2.1 Cloud

FedEarthData cloud providers deliver access to cloud IaaS (e.g. OpenStack) and container orchestration services (e.g. Kubernetes) for the execution and deployment of Copernicus and EO-related workloads as VMs (IaaS) or as containers (container orchestration systems) alongside with the access to data on storage resources that can interoperate with the Data Federation. This base layer provides APIs for the management of the compute and storage resources as a Service that support both upper layers of the architecture and users can interact with them directly. These underlying providers integrate with federated AAI mechanisms so users can seamlessly access them. Cloud providers use EGI Federation central services for centralised monitoring, accounting and federated authentication and authorisation.

2.1.1 Orchestration

C-SCALE orchestration provides users with a seamless deployment of applications across different and heterogeneous infrastructures. The PaaS Orchestrator instantiates resources on Cloud Management Frameworks (like OpenStack, OpenNebula, AWS, Google, Microsoft Azure, etc) and Mesos or Kubernetes clusters expressed through templates written in TOSCA⁸, and then deploys them on the best cloud site available. In order to do that it 1) gathers SLAs, monitoring information and other data from platform services, and 2) asks the cloud provider ranker for a list of the best cloud sites. The exposed REST APIs are consumed by a web dashboard portal that offers a graphical user interface to facilitate the usage of the orchestrator.

⁶ <https://www.egi.eu/service/check-in/>

⁷ <https://wiki.surfnet.nl/display/SRAM/>

⁸ TOSCA Simple Profile in YAML Version 1.0.

<http://docs.oasis-open.org/tosca/TOSCA-Simple-Profile-YAML/v1.0/os/TOSCA-Simple-Profile-YAML-v1.0-os.html>

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In C-SCALE the orchestrator mainly delivers two types of deployments:

- Kubernetes, for the execution of container-based applications.
- openEO (see details below), for a ready-to-use system to access and process Earth observation datasets.

2.1.2 FedEarthData Cloud Providers

2.1.2.1 CESNET

CESNET operates a high-throughput cloud infrastructure based on OpenStack, titled MetaCentrum Cloud, or MCC for short. It provides a basic Infrastructure-as-a-Service interface as well as higher-level services such as object storage and – to a limited extent – platform orchestration. The cloud service is integrated with multiple large-scale identity federations, namely with the national e-Infra.CZ, with the Elixir life science federation, and – most importantly for C-SCALE – also with EGI Check-in. Many higher-level services provided in the context of EGI and EOSC are already deployed and tested with MCC. Among them is the PaaS Orchestrator/Infrastructure Manager stack, which can be relied on to deploy custom platforms at the facility.

MetaCentrum Cloud also hosts the EGI Notebooks service, which serves as one of the primary interfaces for interactive computing in C-SCALE.

2.1.2.2 GRNET

GRNET operates a Cloud infrastructure under the OpenStack software. Within the C-SCALE project, both CPU and storage resources are delivered. A total of 56 CPU cores over several Virtual Machines (VMs) is used for the pre- and post-processing of the HiSea use case’s process flow and tracking, an NFS-Server setup with an additional 300 TB storage for data caching, and a SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog (STAC) endpoint distribution under the resto software (I.e. a metadata catalog and search engine for geospatialized data), which is also registered in the Grid Operations Centre Database (GOODB) service. Among service delivery, GRNET participates in the respective project’s communication channels such as GitHub discussion boards, use case meetings, and Cloud support.

2.1.2.3 INCD

INCD provides computing and data services to the national and international scientific and academic community in all areas of knowledge. The infrastructure is especially oriented to provide scientific computing services, supporting researchers and the participation in national and international projects. The INCD technical team provides very close user support, offering solutions tailored to the needs and specificities of each project. INCD operates an integrated infrastructure with services being provided from multiple locations, interconnected by a state-of-the-art data network. Its services are integrated in international infrastructures with which it shares computing resources for the benefit of projects of national and international relevance. In this context, INCD participates in

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EGI, the Iberian computing infrastructure (IBERGRID)⁹, the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG)¹⁰, and EOSC through the EOSC-synergy, EGI-ACE and C-SCALE projects.

2.1.2.4 CloudFerro

CloudFerro provides innovative cloud services. It delivers and operates cloud computing platforms for specialized markets such as the European space sector, climate research and science, with extensive experience in storing and processing big data sets including multipetabyte repositories of Earth Observation satellite data. In C-SCALE, CloudFerro offers a flexible OpenStack-based cloud solution and dedicated technical support delivered by an experienced local team with unique competencies. CloudFerro is the largest company in the space sector in Poland and a major one in Europe. We have been trusted by leading European firms and scientific institutions from various big-data-processing market sectors, including the European Space Agency (ESA), the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT), German Aerospace Centre (DLR) and many others. CloudFerro is the only Polish company in the space sector that has the status of the prime contractor for the above-mentioned institutions.

2.1.2.5 INFN

INFN has developed open innovative solutions for advanced distributed computing and software applications for more than two decades. It has a remarkable and recognized expertise in Grid and Cloud technologies, having fostered and participated, with leadership roles, in several large projects financed by the EC, that promoted the realization of the EGI Federation and the EOSC. In C-SCALE INFN delivers resources from the ReCaS-Bari center, which is developed and implemented by the University of Bari “Aldo Moro” and by INFN through the ReCaS project. ReCaS-Bari has about 10.000 CPU cores, 5 Petabytes of disk storage and 3 Petabytes of tape storage. The Cloud@ReCaS infrastructure is based on OpenStack and has about 1700 CPU cores, 7 TB of RAM and 270 TB of storage.

2.1.2.6 EODC

EODC provides a cloud computing environment for the Earth Observation ground segment for deriving geophysical parameters and land cover properties from Sentinel-1 (synthetic aperture radar), Sentinel-2 (high-resolution optical imaging) and other EO missions. EODC’s infrastructure consists of a central storage element based on a multi-petabyte disk and tape storage (EODC Storage, >20PB) that is connected to a co-located cloud computing infrastructure based on OpenStack (EODC Cloud), a specific near-realtime processing environment (EODC Processor) and 2 high-performance compute systems (EODC HPC, i.e., the Vienna Scientific Cluster VSC-4 and VSC-5 connected to the EODC Storage, see <https://vsc.ac.at//systems/>). Additionally, the EODC infrastructure consists of a specific tape-based backup storage (EODC Backup) and is connected to the Austrian meteorologic institute (ZAMG, since 01.01.2023 Geosphere Austria¹¹). The whole EODC

⁹ <https://www.ibergrid.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://wlcg.web.cern.ch/>

¹¹ <https://www.geosphere.at/>

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infrastructure is embedded in the Austrian academic network ACOnet¹² that ensures its connectivity and high data rates within the European academic network GÉANT. In addition, EODC is a federation partner of the WEKEO DIAS activity¹³ since 2018.

2.2 HTC/HPC

In the HTC/HPC federation, we focused on delivering seamless access integration for users across distributed cluster systems by making use of federated and IdP validated identities. We do this by making use of SRAM as the collaboration tool. It is developed at SURF, the Dutch NREN. It supports SAML, OIDC, LDAP, and SCIM to convey (collaborative) organisation, group and membership information to service providers (SPs). It also offers a web interface to create and manage those organisations, groups and members (i.e., users). SRAM itself is composed of a front end and a back end. The front end is developed by SURF, while for the back end, eduTEAMS is used.

2.2.1 SRAM

In SRAM personal information is stored: an e-mail address, first name, surname, etc. In order to comply with the GDPR and SURF not taking the role of the data controller, the concept of organisations is introduced in SRAM. It is the organisation that must take responsibility for the data underneath it. SURF then acts as a data processor for those organisations. Before a legal entity may become an organisation in SRAM, it must sign a data processor agreement.

An organisation is a structure under which groups and their users are managed. Within SRAM there are two levels of groups. The first level is that of a project; a number of people from several institutions collaborate for that project. This overarching group is called a Collaborative Organisation (CO). Users are, at a minimum, always a member of a CO. Projects can be divided into smaller groups, or simply groups. This can be used to make certain CO members members of a CO group. These groups for example are used by one of the providers to allow users access to resources.

Once you have a CO in SRAM and possibly already filled with the first users and groups, the CO must be linked to an SP. As long as that has not happened, an SP will not receive any information from SRAM concerning that CO. Within SRAM the CO admin can search for the correct SP and opt to link with it. However, an SP can require that it must approve the link request first. As soon as a CO is correctly linked to an SP the SP can start receiving attributes through either SAML, OIDC, SCIM or LDAP. For the latter, however, there is a small delay as the SRAM LDAP needs to be filled first.

For the web world, getting the attributes is a bit easier, as this is part of the user trying to use the web service, compared to the non-web world i.e., LDAP. When a user uses a browser to connect to a web service, that user must either make use of the SAML or OIDC protocol. Either protocol supplies the attributes to the SP as part of the initiated flow. For LDAP and SCIM however, this will not happen automatically. There is no push mechanism in SRAM and therefore SP must pull the information themselves. For SCIM, there is a notification system so that SPs can be informed of any changes. This alleviates the SP from regular polling of SRAM. For both LDAP and SCIM, the SP must read the attributes and update its own local LDAP accordingly. Once done, all the group and

¹² <https://www.aco.net>

¹³ <https://www.wekeo.eu/news/december-2018-check-our-wekeo-latestupdates>

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membership information should be in the local LDAP of the SP, and users should be able to use the service based on the group and membership information in SRAM. As an SP you only get to see a partial view or in LDAP terms a subtree. This subtree will only contain COs, and thereby those group and membership information, that are successfully linked with the SP. This ensures that SPs won't be able to view any other information what that is theirs.

In C-SCALE we co-developed, implemented and distributed SRAMsync¹⁴. This open-source software allows SPs to sync their local LDAP-based (currently the standard for HTC/HPC systems) identity management system with those parts of the central SRAM-hosted LDAP database that are required for coupling their service (in this case a cluster system) with SRAM-hosted collaborative organisations (CO). Here the CO represents the research team which for C-SCALE is equal to a use case. The COs for C-SCALE are initially created by a mandated C-SCALE organisation (in this case EGI Foundation) for the FedEarthData service then the CO admin role is delegated to the PI of the use case. This way the PI can self-organize his or her team and provide granular access (via group management) for team members to those services that the CO has access to. Furthermore, to ease team management, the PI if so chooses can also delegate the CO admin role to one or more team members in the CO. SRAMsync has been developed with support for multiple SPs in mind. There is no one-size-fits-all when it comes to how SPs have organised their identity and access management (IAM) systems. SRAMsync supports a plugin architecture where each SP can implement the interaction with their IAM, while SRAMsync reads and processes the SRAM LDAP subtree and passes on any changes in the SRAM LDAP it detects between successive runs.

It is important to note here that the services a CO in SRAM can be coupled to are not limited to FedEarthData. A CO can request access to any service that is available via SRAM. Furthermore, this access is also not limited by the LDAP protocol, rather as stated above SRAM also supports access to services via SAML, OIDC and SCIM for the same federated user identity. In C-SCALE we show an example of this functionality by providing access via LDAP to the non-web-based SURF Delena HTC platform and also providing access to the accompanying web-based monitoring dashboards using OIDC for the same user identity.

2.2.2 HTC/HPC providers

2.2.2.1 SURF

SURF provides the Data Processing (Delena and Spider), Spider storage and dCache installations for C-SCALE. These offer HTC computing and storage for approved C-SCALE use cases. Access to these non-web services is provided via SSH keys using the LDAP protocol and SRAMsync. The computing platforms Spider and Delena do not just offer single-user access, but rather are aimed at collaborative teams, hence they support more complex role-based access as part of project spaces (<https://spiderdocs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/Pages/about.html#collaboration>). To ensure that the correct roles are assigned and can be managed, a CO in SRAM upon coupling with the service is presented with SP-defined service groups in SRAM. The CO admin then assigns roles to CO members by placing them in the appropriate service groups.

¹⁴ <https://github.com/SURFscz/SRAMsync>

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Delena does not only provide SSH access to its computing service. It also offers an auxiliary service called the Delena monitoring service. This is a Grafana web service that displays a number of jobs and cluster health metrics for Delena. Access to this service is not possible via SSH keys. Instead, it supports the OIDC protocol. As discussed in Section 2.2, we have made the Delena monitoring service available to C-SCALE COs via SRAM, allowing CO members to use their single federated identity to access both services.

2.2.2.2 GRNET

GRNET provides the ARIS HPC cluster as an HPC service for C-SCALE. Within this project, two use cases are allocated. Both use cases have access to computation in the CPU domain, while one of them additionally, to GPU. GRNET participates in the C-SCALE HPC federation. Specifically, it monitors for user changes with the use of the SRAMsync tool. An e-mail notification upon a user event to the GRNET's HPC support triggers the interaction for further processing (e.g., account creation in the HPC cluster, SSH keys addition, etc.), which is achieved in a manual manner and after communicating with the involved people. Additionally, GRNET participates in all respective project's communication channels such as GitHub discussion boards, use case meetings, and HPC support.

2.2.2.3 TU Wien

TUW provides access to the VSC clusters as an HPC service for C-SCALE. TUW has successfully integrated its local user (identity) management system with SRAM using SRAMsync. Unlike GRNET and SURF, access to the VSC clusters requires SSH keys in combination with telephone number-based two-factor authentication (2FA). A telephone number for a user is not an attribute that is normally released by an IdP, hence it is not available for CO members within SRAM. Discussions are ongoing between SURF and TUW to understand how this missing information can be filled in to provide access compliant with the VSC access mechanism to C-SCALE users. Once resolved the VSC cluster will be fully integrated with the C-SCALE HPC/HTC federation.

2.3 openEO

The openEO API allows access to and processing of Earth observation datasets. It is designed to be compatible with large-scale processing systems¹⁵. The design also enables a federated setup that allows multiple compute infrastructures to be offered via a single endpoint (the openEO aggregator). openEO is a standard that can use various implementations¹⁶ as backend. The choice of implementation typically depends on the maturity and the compatibility of the technology stack with the provider infrastructure and knowledge. Within FedEarthData, C-SCALE provides access to customised openEO deployments that are either provider-managed or completely self-managed by the users.

In this project, the open source 'Geotrellis' backend was selected for a number of providers, mainly because it is fully open source, includes deployment scripts, and it was the most mature and

¹⁵ <https://openeo.org/documentation/1.0/developers/backends/performance.html>

¹⁶ openEO back-ends: <https://openeo.org/software.html#back-ends>

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complete implementation. One other implementation, based on Dask and Xarray was offered by EODC.

2.3.1 openEO Geotrellis implementation

openEO does not imply a specific architecture, so we detail the Geotrellis deployment here, which was most frequently used in the project. The Geotrellis implementation translates openEO process graphs into Apache Spark jobs.

2.3.1.1 EO Data access

For data access, it requires a STAC catalog (as offered by the C-SCALE data federation). The STAC catalog returns items that need to contain the exact location of the EO raster files in GeoTIFF or JPEG2000 format that need to be processed. This location can be a local path that is mounted directly in the Spark cluster, an S3 URL, or a (public) HTTP URL.

The software will read from the raster asset locations directly, which means that there is a major impact of reading performance on overall job performance. A provider thus needs to choose an optimal setup when configuring collections in the openEO backend. This can mean building a 'local' mirror of EO data, i.e. building a mirror in the same datacentre where the processing is run, or relying on a network connection towards remote datasets. Experiments in the project have shown that there is no single solution, as there are different trade-offs to be made. There's also continuous evolution in available network bandwidth between compute and data providers, which influences the most optimal choice.

When deciding on the best strategy, the compute provider needs to consider these questions:

- What volume of data do I want to mirror locally, and at what cost?
- Do I build a dynamic local cache, or can I select a relevant spatiotemporal extent for a target user group?
- What is the performance & cost of accessing a given remote data archive?
- Do my users favour fast-running jobs, or is overall runtime, not an issue?

2.3.1.2 Kubernetes deployment

Spark jobs can run on various cluster resource managers. The most prevalent system among C-SCALE cloud providers is Kubernetes, so we detail that deployment here. Technical details and Helm charts can be found in the corresponding open-source repository¹⁷

These are the key aspects of this deployment:

1. The main openEO web application is also a Spark application, which runs the synchronous openEO calls¹⁸
2. openEO batch jobs are separate Spark applications. This enables sandboxing for security, and full flexibility in configuring Spark settings.

¹⁷ <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-geotrellis-kubernetes>

¹⁸ <https://api.openeo.org/#tag/Data-Processing/operation/compute-result>

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3. spark-on-k8s-operator¹⁹ is used to configure and deploy Spark applications.
4. A separate 'job-tracker' Kubernetes cron job is responsible for batch job lifecycle management.
5. A Zookeeper cluster is used for persistence of openEO resources
6. Object storage is used to store results.
7. Logs are stored in Elasticsearch by Filebeat, enabling user logs²⁰
8. Auxiliary (optional) components for monitoring: Prometheus, Grafana, Spark history

Figure 2. openEO Geotrellis implementation

2.3.2 Self-deployment of openEO in FedEarthData

INFN has developed a TOSCA template²¹ that allows users to automatically deploy the openEO Platform on cloud resources through the PaaS Orchestrator. The template has been integrated with the PaaS Orchestrator Web Dashboard making it available to the users of the different use cases. The automatic deployment is performed in two steps: 1) a Kubernetes cluster is provisioned with the number and the size of nodes defined by the user; 2) the openEO Platform is installed using the provided helm charts. The whole process, from the provisioning of the needed resources (virtual machines, security groups, public/private IPs, etc.) up to the service installation and configuration, is completely automated and does not require any user interaction. Indeed, the user needs only to

¹⁹ <https://github.com/GoogleCloudPlatform/spark-on-k8s-operator>

²⁰ <https://api.openeo.org/#tag/Batch-Jobs/operation/debug-job>

²¹ <https://github.com/indigo-paas/tosca-templates/blob/main/kubernetes/openeo.yaml>, ansible role <https://github.com/c-scale-community/ansible-role-openeo-k8s>, and tutorial

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define the initial input parameters required to customize the deployment and these data can be provided through a simple and user-friendly web interface (see Figure 3).

OpenEO platform

Description: Deploy the OpenEO platform on kubernetes cluster

Requirements: Create an entry in the Dynamic DNS for accessing your services:

1. Login at <https://nsupdate.fedcloud.eu/>
2. Click on Overview and then on Add Host
3. Type in the hostname you'd like to register and select the domain to use
4. The portal will then show you a secret. You have to copy that secret in the field `dyn_dns_service_token` and the hostname you have chosen in the field `frontend_dns_name` in the form below.

For more information, please visit the [documentation](#).

Deployment description
description

Configuration **Advanced**

admin_token
Enter your password
password token for accessing k8s dashboard

catalog_url
`https://raw.githubusercontent.com/Open-EO/openeo-geotrellis-kubernetes/master/docker/cscale_layercatalog.json`
Layer catalog URL (JSON format)

frontend_dns_name
DNS name for the main k8s endpoints (api server, dashboard, monitoring)

dyn_dns_service_token
Enter your password
Copy here the secret generated by the Dynamic DNS service

certificate_issuer
letsencrypt-prod
Select an issuer for the endpoints SSL certificate

admin_email
Specify the email address for receiving notifications

number_of_nodes
3
number of K8s node VMs

num_cpus_node
4
number of CPUs for K8s node VM

mem_size_node
8 GB
memory size for K8s node VM

ports
Add rule
Ports to open on the K8s master VM

master_flavor
--Select--
Number of vCPUs and memory size of the k8s master VM

Submit Cancel

Figure 3. openEO deployment setup

EGI's Dynamic DNS²² is used to create a DNS name that will be automatically associated with the cluster master IP and is used to access the deployed services through a nginx ingress.

The user can specify the password that will be configured as an admin token to access the Kubernetes and Grafana dashboards, the chosen DNS name, the certificate type that will be used to secure the service endpoints on https (self-signed or Let's Encrypt can be chosen), the flavour of the master and worker nodes.

²² <https://nsupdate.fedcloud.eu/>

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Figure 4. openEO deployment outputs

Once the deployment is complete, the PaaS Orchestrator dashboard provides the outputs of the deployment as shown in the figure above. The outputs include information needed to access both the Kubernetes cluster and the openEO service (see Figure 4). Concerning the Kubernetes cluster, the deployment also includes the installation and configuration of some monitoring tools, based on Prometheus for collecting metrics from the nodes (through NodeExporter), the containers running on the nodes (through cAdvisor) and Kubernetes itself (through KubeEagle). The data can be

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visualized through Grafana: some ready-to-use dashboards are automatically provided for the user to monitor the services status and the resources usage.

Figure 5. Grafana dashboards for Kubernetes

The TOSCA template provides a functional openEO endpoint deployment, although issues in the asynchronous job evaluation are still to be fixed.

2.3.3 Provider-managed deployments

2.3.3.1 INCD openEO

INCD has deployed a Kubernetes cluster on top of an OpenStack cluster to support C-SCALE use cases, using a gitops approach. We created a repository with all the configuration files needed to set up the cluster and the services, and created pipelines to deploy each one of the components. The Kubernetes cluster is composed of 10 nodes with 16 cores and 32 GB of RAM each where openEO is deployed. The first approach was to create a single volume of 12TB for the storage of data for the Aquamonitor use case, but it has been changed to an S3 bucket that is mounted on every single compute node, allowing for the sharing of data both within the cluster and the outside world. A local STAC server has been deployed to download satellite imagery products directly to an S3 Bucket which is then used by openEO.

A Python script was developed to register the metadata of the downloaded products in the user STAC catalogue available at CESNET, in this way all the data that is stored in our S3 bucket can be discovered on the catalogue at CESNET.

2.3.3.2 HTC/HPC openEO

An experiment was carried out to determine if openEO could run on Delena HTC platform at SURF. This showed that it is indeed possible to adapt the Geotrellis implementation to these kinds of resources.

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The proof of concept consisted of deploying a Spark cluster on top of the HTC resources managed by Slurm. Subsequently, openEO is deployed on top of the Spark cluster by a using Geotrellis container (converted from Docker into Singularity) that contains the openEO software that can run the user's openEO job. The results of these experiments are further detailed in openEO GitHub repository²³

Full openEO support would require running a dedicated web service with some additions to be able to submit Slurm-based batch jobs, as it now only supports Kubernetes and YARN jobs. Next to using the Geotrellis backend, there is also the possibility that other backends like the one based on Dask/Xarray are well-suited to run on HPC.

2.4 Notebooks

Jupyter Lab – an online environment to manage and run Jupyter Notebooks, has been selected as the interactive analytic environment for C-SCALE FedEarthData. In terms of processing capacity, it is backed by the members of the C-SCALE Cloud Federation already detailed above.

Jupyter Notebooks are a popular form of interactive publication that can trigger separate steps of data processing, be it minor computations performed locally, or large-scale job collections submitted to other available resources. The major contribution to an existing Jupyter notebooks environment consists in seamless integration with available data and computing resources in C-SCALE.

C-SCALE does not operate its own Jupyter Lab instance, but rather contributes to a pre-existing one – the EGI Notebooks operated by CESNET. It already offered integration with multiple relevant services within the EOSC ecosystem, such as the OneData/OneZone storage, CVMFS storage, DIRAC grid middleware, etc. C-SCALE further extends it to integrate with Copernicus data resources involved in the C-SCALE Data federation (both for lookup and data access), or Cloud compute resources provided in the C-SCALE Cloud federation.

This integration allows users to work interactively with their Jupyter notebook and have the services federation seamlessly available within. In a typical workflow, a user can:

1. Log into the Jupyter Lab service using their identity.
2. Look up applicable Earth observation data through the discovery service provided by the C-SCALE Data federation.
3. Use the same identity (based on a token inserted into the notebook for them on start) to obtain said data from Data federation sites.
4. Perform local analytics or, again, use the same identity to deploy and manage additional compute resources across the cloud federation.

2.5 Software Distribution

FedEarthData is open for different software distribution tools that can match the needs of the providers and users. As a preferred solution, containers are promoted for facilitating the portability

²³ <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-geotrellis-kubernetes/blob/master/hpc/hpc.md>

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of applications from one provider to another, although specially in HPC/HTC systems, re-compilation with the appropriate runtime environment may be required.

For IaaS clouds, users can rely on EGI’s Application Database which offers a cloud marketplace where users can register Virtual Machine (VM) images with the needed software. VM images in AppDB are organised in collections curated by communities (Virtual Organizations or VOs) and these are then automatically distributed to the providers. Normally these VM images contain the basic Operating System and utilities to run the containerised applications on top. See for example the VM images of the coastmonitor.c-scale.eu VO in Figure 6.

Figure 6. AppDB images for coastmonitor.c-scale.eu VO

Application containers can be stored in any compatible container repository. There are well-known repositories where users can store their containers (e.g., DockerHub, quay.io). As part of C-SCALE we are testing two options as default repository: the GitHub package repository, which provides support for containers and other types of software artifacts that can be associated with the C-SCALE community organisation in GitHub (see Figure 7); and CESNET’s Harbor²⁴-based container repository that is accessible to C-SCALE users (see Figure 8). Both options are compatible with Docker and OCI (Open Container Initiative) compatible runtimes.

²⁴ <https://goharbor.io/>

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Figure 7. GitHub package repository for C-SCALE Community

Figure 8. CESNET Container registry

2.6 Access to data in FedEarthData

Typically, users will act independently and access Earth observation data from cloud/HTC/HPC resources as they see fit, directly from data providers. In other words, no long-term storage of input data on compute sites is expected – they should be brought in “on the fly” from Data federation sites. It is however also possible for users to enter into closer cooperation with the resource provider, who can decide to cache a set of the required data locally, at their site.

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2.6.1 Accessing data directly from the Data federation

Accessing Copernicus Earth observation data from cloud resources within the FedEarthData service is intended to be seamless. This is helped by the fact that the C-SCALE Cloud federation and the C-SCALE Data federation share authentication and authorization (AAI) technologies and recognize the same authentication tokens. I.e., the same identity used by a given user to instantiate resources in the cloud infrastructure can also be used to access primary data from the Data federation sites.

When using the cloud resource interactively, there is always the option to authenticate manually in a browser window before accessing data. For robotic (unattended) access, authentication is realized by means of an OIDC access (bearer) token, which can be obtained in multiple ways: from the EGI token Web site²⁵, from an OIDC refresh token, but the simplest approach is having the token inserted into a freshly instantiated virtual machine when the user first creates it in the cloud.

Data can then be accessed by any standard web client (library).

2.6.2 Caching data by compute resource providers

For various reasons a resource provider may decide to cater specifically to a selection of use cases, and cache data they may require locally (in terms of infrastructure) to speed up access. They may even go as far as unpacking the data, pre-processing, annotating, making them available on a read-write filesystem, etc. In the context of C-SCALE, this has been done, e.g., by the provider INCD for the members of the AquaMonitor use case.

To facilitate this, C-SCALE has provided a User-level STAC catalogue – a metadata service, which can be used by the provider to register data they have prepared for the use cases, and through that registration to make the data discoverable to the users of their site. Subsequently, the catalogue can be used by users to identify the data they need.

It is important to note that metadata records created in this manner in the user-level catalogue do not have global applicability, as they may be inserted – for example – with local paths to data, valid only within a single provider’s site. Therefore, these records are not included in global searches for data across the FedEarthData service and stand separately as an aid to user groups and their partners, who have registered them.

2.6.3 Interim Data and Results

Similar to input data, the outputs of analyses run on computing resources in the federation are not expected to remain indefinitely. Interim data, existing between consequential stages of a workflow, can be stored on site, with storage capacity provided under the normal “Infrastructure as a service” (IaaS) paradigm. Final results can be stored temporarily, and then removed into a more permanent location for publishing. This can be done completely independently from C-SCALE (e.g., through Zenodo or simply by storing the data at the users’ premises), but it is also possible to negotiate with a selected partner in the C-SCALE Data federation, whether they wish to carry the results of the analyses. If so, a mechanism for transferring the data (pull/push) is negotiated, as well as responsibilities for generating metadata for the results. This process is not yet standardized and

²⁵<https://aai.egi.eu/token/>

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depends on mutual agreement between the use case, who generates the data, and the provider responsible for their redistribution.

This lack of formalized procedure is there for two reasons:

1. There have been few actual cases where a use case was actually interested in making their results available publicly in FedEarthData, which means that there is no notion of *common* requirements that such a standardized process should address.
2. Making the data ready for public redistribution requires additional effort, such as proper and systemic generation of metadata, and not every use case can find the capacity.

Once these resulting products are made available from the Data federation in this manner, they become discoverable and accessible from the FedEarthData service.

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3 openEO Platform

The openEO Platform implements the openEO API via a federated approach. This is a completely managed offer where users do not need to worry about the specific details of the openEO deployment, they only need to interact with the API and standard functions of openEO to work with the EO data. openEO Platform can be used within Jupyter Notebooks, within an Integrated Development Environment (IDE) through openEO client libraries (e.g., Python client), for M2M integration through REST API or directly through the openEO Web Editor (also known as openEO Platform Editor). openEO Platform is supported in C-SCALE via EODC and VITO and it is planned to be expanded to new providers in the future. The requirements for other providers to join this openEO federation are still under preparation, but will include:

- Requirements on minimal quality level (by providing an OLA)
- Requirements on the minimal feature set
- Integration with a shared accounting system

The federation design mainly relies on the openEO aggregator component²⁶, which can be seen as a proxy that simply forwards incoming requests based on a set of rules. For instance, a process that loads data from a specific collection will be forwarded to a backend that offers this collection.

openEO was documented in detail in D3.3 and extensive information on the platform and its features is available online²⁷. openEO uses OIDC (OpenID Connect) to authenticate via an external service given a client ID. For C-SCALE, this means authenticating through EGI Check-in service.

²⁶ <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-aggregator>

²⁷ <https://openeo.cloud/>

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4 EOSC integration

C-SCALE aims at expanding the EOSC offer to support Copernicus and Earth Observation data analytics. FedEarthData and openEO Platform are in the process of being onboarded into the EOSC Portal. A complete specification following the EOSC Resource Profile v4.0²⁸ was developed by C-SCALE for these services, thus the services are compliant with the Rules for Participation and Interoperability Framework of EOSC. Once onboarded, these services will be available and orderable via the EOSC Marketplace.

The AAI technical solutions used in C-SCALE (EGI Check-in and SRAM) are already compliant with the existing EOSC AAI guidelines. Both systems build on the previous work done by both AARC and AARC2²⁹ projects and the ongoing AEGIS group³⁰ that have contributed to establishing the architecture for the EOSC AAI with the definition of the AARC Blueprint Architecture (BPA)³¹, which enables easy access to services and shared resources in order to collaborate. The work done to integrate SRAM and EGI Check-in shows the interoperability between the two systems to allow users registered in one of them to access both HPC/HTC and Cloud resources.

FedEarthData relied on the EOSC Helpdesk³² and has a complete support structure with a 1st line support and a set of 2nd line support units for the different providers of the federation to be able to support users and is configured to properly redirect requests to the already existing helpdesk and support structures of each provider.

FedEarthData cloud providers leverage the existing EGI Cloud Federation components for accounting and monitoring. These are already compatible with their EOSC counterparts or are in the process of being fully integrated. In the case of HTC and HPC providers, we investigated how to centralize monitoring and accounting. We identified potential pathways on how this could be done by making use of EOSC Core services. However, significant development effort is needed by both C-SCALE and the EOSC Core service providers to implement this in a secure and sustainable manner. This effort is not available and hence, within the C-SCALE project, we decided to focus on decentralized monitoring and accounting already available at each of the providers and update the FedEarthData documentation on how to use these.

C-SCALE Compute Federation follows existing EOSC-hub technical specifications³³ (such as the ones for Cloud Compute and PaaS Solutions), since there are no equivalent specifications from EOSC yet. It should be noted, though, that C-SCALE participates in relevant interoperability groups such as the Compute Continuum Working Group to jointly provide a specification that can describe computing resources in the EOSC context.

²⁸ <https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/B.+v4.00+EOSC+Resource+Profile>

²⁹ <https://aarc-project.eu/>

³⁰ <https://aarc-project.eu/about/aegis/>

³¹ <https://aarc-project.eu/architecture/>

³² <https://eosc-helpdesk.eosc-portal.eu/>

³³ EOSC-hub technical documentation: <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/technical-documentation>

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5 Conclusions

The C-SCALE Compute Federation provides access to a wide range of computing providers (IaaS VMs, container orchestration platforms, HPC and HTC systems, Notebooks and openEO) to enable the analysis of Copernicus and Earth observation data through the EOSC Portal. The design of this federation has allowed C-SCALE to deliver two new service offers for EOSC: FedEarthData and the openEO Platform. These bring a flexible approach to allow users to deploy their applications using federated authentication mechanisms, run their workflows on different computing systems, and have access to data using C-SCALE Data Federation tools. The federation relies on existing (TRL ≥ 8) tools and services already compliant with EOSC, thus facilitating the integration into the larger EOSC ecosystem of providers.

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